

COVID-19 lockdowns and the thermostat

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A recently published article is titled, “The Covid-19 lesson from Sweden: Don’t lock down” (Andersson and Jonung, 2024). However, this title misrepresents the article, and the article fails to account for economic logic. For reference, I reproduce the key figures of their article, which observe no strong correlation across countries between lockdown stringency and excess deaths (Fig. 1a), and a negative correlation between lockdown stringency and GDP growth (Fig. 1b).

In fact, Sweden did impose mandatory restrictions early in the pandemic. Though less restrictive than many other countries, these included a ban on large gatherings. As the authors admit in the article, “we cannot evaluate the impact of a *zero* lockdown policy” (Andersson and Jonung, 2024, p. 5). It is therefore mysterious why, with their title, they attempt to do just this.

Moving to the article itself, the authors in one place admit that Fig. 1a “does not settle the issue of causality,” raising the question of why they attempted to draw causal lessons about lockdowns. This is answered in the next sentence, which claims that Fig. 1a at least illustrates “that countries with more stringent lockdown measures did not experience a lower death rate, as might be expected *a priori*” (Andersson and Jonung, 2024, p. 5). However, this expectation does not reflect economic logic. Consider the thermostat analogy of Milton Friedman (2003).

A thermostat’s purpose is to keep a house at a constant temperature. When the weather outside is cold, the thermostat turns up, and when the weather outside is warm, the thermostat

Figure 1. a) regression of percent excess deaths vs. degree of lockdown defined by the Hale index. B) regression of percent GDP growth vs. degree of lockdown defined by the Hale index. Reproduced from (Andersson and Jonung, 2024, Figs. 3 & 4). Andersson and Jonung suggest that “the health benefits of lockdowns appear to be weak when judged by the excess death rate,” while “it is fairly easy to conclude that the economic costs of lockdowns were substantial” (2024, p. 6).

Figure 2. A simple model in which lockdowns are assumed to work, and countries are assumed to choose their lockdown stringency based on covid threat level. Covid threat defined as expected excess deaths if no lockdown occurs; stringency defined as lives saved by lockdown. a) Countries' stringency functions may less than compensate for covid threat; exactly compensate for covid threat; or more than compensate for covid threat. b) these three stringency functions yield different predictions about the relationship between excess death and lockdown stringency. If lockdowns work, but stringency less than compensates for covid threat, then more stringent lockdowns will be associated with higher excess death.

turns down. But if one were to graph the thermostat's settings against the temperatures inside the house, one would find no correlation, precisely *because* the thermostat is working correctly. Likewise, the purpose of a COVID-19 lockdown is to mitigate the threat of COVID-19 illness and death. *A priori*, we would expect that insofar as countries had any ability to discern the level of COVID-19 threat, they likely chose the stringency of their lockdowns accordingly. To a first approximation, it is therefore plausible that *if lockdowns are effective, we should expect no correlation between lockdown stringency and excess deaths.*

More precisely, the expected relationship depends on countries' stringency functions with respect to covid threat level (which may depend on how countries prioritize health versus social costs). Figure 2 illustrates a simple model. In this model, covid threat level is defined as expected number of excess deaths assuming no lockdown; stringency is defined as expected number of lives saved by lockdown (i.e., this model assumes that lockdowns do work); and countries choose their lockdown stringency as an increasing linear function of covid threat level. In this model, depending on whether the slope of the stringency vs. threat curve is steeper or shallower than 1 (Fig. 2a), excess deaths can decrease, remain constant, or even increase as lockdown stringency increases (Fig. 2b). It is therefore plausible that *if lockdowns are effective, but severe covid threats are not compensated for by equivalently stringent lockdowns, we should expect a positive correlation between excess deaths and lockdown stringency.*

A lesson of economics is that all interpretations of data invoke theoretical assumptions about behaviour. Andersson and Jonung seem to assume that countries' lockdown stringencies were determined randomly w.r.t. COVID-19 threat level, rather than chosen to meet the threat.

Yet nowhere do they defend this theoretical assumption; indeed, it is unclear whether they were aware they'd theorized this, as opposed to being “accidental theorists” (Krugman, 1997).

My critique here considers only the logic of (Andersson and Jonung, 2024); it does not attempt a full evaluation of Sweden's policies. For a discussion by an independent commission formed by the Swedish government, see (Coronakommissionen, 2022). That commission was in some ways supportive of the choice to focus on voluntary distancing, but also recommended more and earlier restrictions of certain indoor areas and large social gatherings. This is worth considering, given the role of super-spreading in COVID-19 (Lewis, 2021; Nielsen et al., 2023).

The COVID-19 pandemic has had enormous health and social costs. It is essential that we learn from it (Sachs et al., 2022). Drawing the correct lessons will require extensive open, inclusive deliberation (Norheim et al., 2021), informed by honest communication of sound interpretations of accurate data (Bahry, 2023). This is not only out of respect for the public, but also a matter of rational self-interest; when the next pandemic comes, today's discussions may determine whether we live or die. I am thankful for this opportunity to clarify one, commonly-misunderstood, narrow aspect of one of the many thorny issues that will need to be discussed.

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